

Original Article

Myth of Sisyphus: Mobile Phone User as a Replica of Sisyphus in the Contemporary Era

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Abstract

meaningless, irrational, and purposeless, yet recognizing it, human beings always search for it, even acknowledging its absence. Thus, the term "absurdity" is introduced by the French philosopher and writer Albert Camus; he describes absurdity as the gap between human desires and the universe's silence. He uses the character of Sisyphus and his eternal punishment as an example of absurdism, as Sisyphus was well aware of his situation and faced it wholeheartedly to balance the complex situation. In the contemporary age, mobile phone users act as a modern Sisyphus as they are trapped in an endless situation of repetition and scrolling in the cycle of social media algorithms in search of happiness and meaning, yet they know their addiction and its helpless nature regarding their questions, but they continue to search for it. This ongoing struggle, with no possible resolution, leads to an existential crisis of absurdism. The study is qualitative in nature. By keeping in view the theoretical framework of absurdism, this study reveals that the user of a mobile phone would be able to regain control, redefine their aims, and face their condition with open eyes and wholeheartedly. On the other hand, the study shows that the user would be apprehensive of their condition and rebel against the endless algorithmic manipulation; it is not defeated by absurdity. The mobile users embrace absurdity like Sisyphus, finding meaning in the struggle itself. Thus, the findings pave the path for future researchers and addictive users of technology by offering a new philosophical framework to understand the psychological and emotional toll of digital addiction.

Keywords: Digital Absurdity, Absurdist Philosophy, Mobile Phone, Sisyphus Cycle, Addiction

Introduction

Danish philosopher Søren Kierkegaard is considered a pioneer to introduce the concept of "absurd" in 1840. He believes that absurdity explores the difficulties faced by human beings throughout their lives, which arise due to the conflict between religious faith and human reasoning in search of meaning. It is due to the acceptance of some irrational things through religious beliefs. His work titled "Fear and Trembling" (1843) introduces absurdism -- which is something beyond logic, reason, and rationality. At the beginning of the 20th century, "absurdism" was reshaped by French-Algerian writer and philosopher Albert Camus during the European existential movement. In the famous work of Albert Camus titled "*The Myth of Sisyphus*" (Le Mythe de Sisyphe, 1942). Here he denies some of the core concepts of the early philosophical ideologies regarding existentialism and nihilism by introducing absurdism.

Absurdity is a philosophy based on the notion that the universe is irrational, purposeless, and meaningless, but acknowledging this, humans will continuously search for it despite its absence. This movement is closely related to the existentialist movements of the 20th century, particularly through the works of French philosopher and writer Albert Camus' "Myth of Sisyphus" (1942). According to him, absurdity is the gap between human desires and the universe's indifference. In the contemporary age, mobile phone addiction acts as a modern form of absurdity, where the users are trapped in a situation where they realize that the excessive usage of mobile phones is

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meaningless, yet they continue to search for it. This ongoing struggle, with no possible resolution, leads to an existential crisis or absurdism.

Many scholars have yet to work on exploring this issue of excessive usage of mobile phones through quantitative and qualitative research by only focusing on particular populations. Despite efforts to address the issue of over-usage of mobile phones and its consequences, ongoing initiatives have failed to bridge significant gaps, especially of being absurd in today's modern and digital world. This study addresses the urgent need to stop the over- and misuse of mobile phones. Through excessive usage of mobile phones, individuals are trapped in a cycle of absurdism, in a form of repetitive and useless scrolling that truly affects mental health and social behavior. This paradoxical modern globalized world, due to mobile addiction, completely results in an isolated and introverted personality.

Background and Context

The research explores mobile phone addiction, which causes absurdity, which leads to the risk of anxiety, overthinking, depression, and isolation, which causes the increasing effect of different mental diseases, illnesses, sleep untidiness, and social dysfunctions, in the context of exploring Albert Camus's 'The Myth of Sisyphus' and the aimless scrolling of the rock up to the hill and still searching for meaning, joy, and happiness. The meaningless repetition, the endless scrolling, and waiting for endless notifications on mobile phones ultimately create a sense of absurdity, detachment, and alienation, and mobile phone addiction. This topic examines how mobile phones nurture a form of existential loneliness in today's modern, globalized, and interconnected world.

Digital Absurdity

In the contemporary age, mobile phone addiction is one of the crucial and important factors that needs serious attention, particularly among adolescents. This burning issue is highlighted in the context of Chinese society by Xiaofeng Dou and Jiachen Lu's research based on the scientific report 'The impact of depression and anxiety on mobile phone addiction and the mediating effect of self-esteem' (2024). Overuse of mobile phones leads to ridiculous changes among people's intentions in today's paradoxical, modern, digital, and globalized world in the form of isolation, solitude, and separation from real-life situations, which leads to physical, emotional, and mental disturbances in personalities, causing absurdism. Although mobile phones have many advantages and disadvantages, many researchers and scholars have been highlighting the misuse of mobile phones, and some of them have also explored the overusage of mobile phones and its consequences. Saurav Basu (2022), in his article 'Mobile Phone Addiction as an Emerging Behavioral Form of Addiction among Adolescents in India,' explores the over-usage of mobile phones in a community-based study of rural Delhi on a population of approximately 264 adolescents (10 to 19 years old), highlighting the possible health issues due to over-usage of mobile phones among adolescents in urban settings. Hence, it is essential to limit the access to mobile phones for important utility purposes to adolescents.

This research will highlight the burning issue from the perspective of literature as a modern form of absurdity, as absurdity, as explained by Albert Camus (1942) in his work "The Myth of Sisyphus," as the repetitive, endless, and useless cycle of rolling a boulder up to the hill, only to watch it roll back down, and seeking meaning in this meaningless situation, can be aligned with the excessive usage of mobile phones and their endless scrolling for meaning in meaningless platforms.

The Myth of Sisyphus

"The goddess punished Sisyphus because he had discovered the secret of Zeus and because he scorned and rebelled against her," Nader Masarwah (2015).

Albert Camus interprets the absurd during and after the Second World War in 1942. In response to the loss of faith and religion and the tragic results of the large number of destructions after the world wars, he raises the question as to whether there is any justifiable reason against suicide and meaning in absurd situations. Camus describes the absurd as the inability of humans to make sense of their search for meaning and purpose in their own lives. Camus's idea of absurdism explains that life is apparently meaningless, although he is careful to avoid nihilism. He uses the famous Greek myth of Sisyphus as a metaphor for this idea. Sisyphus is punished by the gods to roll a boulder up to the hill again and again, and Sisyphus feels joy and happiness, according to Camus. Camus's point is that if life is hopeless and meaningless, we always have to search for meaning and happiness. Paul Mumme (2016). or accomplishment, and according to Camus, we can imagine Sisyphus happy in this abnormal situation.

Sisyphus was a character in Greek mythology, condemned by the goddess, and his punishment was to continuously roll a boulder up a hill, only to watch it roll back down once he reached the top. The myth symbolizes fruitless effort. The punishment was eternal, repetitive, and without any possibility of escape.

Theoretical Framework

The study employs absurdist philosophy to explore the phenomenon of digital absurdity, particularly focusing on Albert Camus' concept of the Sisyphus cycle as a lens to analyze mobile phone addiction. The framework is used to interpret qualitative data on users' experiences with mobile phone addiction, analyzing their repetitive behaviors and useless scrolling in search of meaning in the light of absurdist philosophy.

Objectives

- To scratch the hidden perspective of being absurd in today's globalized world, due to over-usage of mobile phones, corresponding with Albert Camus' concept of Absurdism.
- To hold the mirror of absurdism to the excessive users of mobile phones and to highlight the most challenging and neglected issue of the contemporary age of mobile addiction.

Research Questions

- Why does mobile phone addiction mirror absurdity in the context of the digital era?
- How can mobile phone addiction be studied as a modern and digital form of absurdity in the perspective of Albert Camus' absurdism?

Problem Statement

The central problem addressed in this study is to explain mobile phone addiction as a modern form of absurdity and its repetitive and endless scrolling as a symbol of searching for meaning, in correspondence with Sisyphus rolling the rock up to the hill, leading to the feelings of existential distress.

Significance of the Study

This research is significant because the research explores a unique interaction between absurdist philosophy and today's modern digital behavior, which has not been explored by any scholar. It will provide a comprehensive understanding of the endless scrolling of mobile phones in search of meaning as a digital or modern form of absurdity. Moreover, it will highlight absurdity as absurdity is defined by Albert Camus in *The Myth of Sisyphus* and how Sisyphus was trapped in an endless and repetitive situation of rolling a boulder up to the hill. Additionally, by bridging knowledge gaps, this research shows the significance of modern absurdity and its solution by controlling the overusage of mobile phones. It will address the most neglected challenge of over usage of mobile phones in today's modern world and one of the main sources of absurdity in contemporary era and societies.

Literature Review

Scholars such as Ms. Achsah Mathew and Mr. Joshy Mathew (2024) argue in their article "Exploring Absurdity in Myth of Sisyphus and Theatre of Absurd," published in *IJHSSM*, that they investigated the elements of absurdity and its solution according to Albert Camus (pp. 821-833). They highlighted the useless and repetitive action of Sisyphus rolling the boulder up to the hill as a never-ending punishment and a permanent form of absurdity, with the book *The Myth of Sisyphus* by Albert Camus and notions of Theatre of the Absurd. According to this article, Camus suggests that by acknowledging the absurdity of existence, one can find a deeper appreciation for life itself. In his book *Myth of Sisyphus*, Camus also gave a solution to deal with the problem of absurdism: to deal with absurdity as a gentleman can cause happiness even in the darkest aspect of life, which can operate as a tool to reduce suicide and overcome the overwhelming and endless form of absurdity.

Kieran Tranter's article, *Sisyphus and the Present: Time in Modern and Digital Legalities* (2022), connects Albert Camus's philosophy of absurdity to the digital age. Tranter argues that Sisyphus, even with his endless and repetitive punishment of rolling a boulder up to the hill, learns to live in the present and finds joy in apparently absurd and meaningless situations. According to him, the repetitive tasks, like "click-work," resemble Sisyphus' struggle. This perspective is relevant to understanding the endless cycle of mobile phone addiction, where users are trapped in repetitive actions but may also find ways to create meaning and connection in the digital world.

EI Mehdi Khachiche, in his academic work *Albert Camus' "The Myth of Sisyphus": Absurdism and the Question of Happiness* (2020-2021), explores Camus' philosophy that people can deal with the absurd—the

conflict between humanity's quest for meaning and the universe's lack of it—and Camus chooses Sisyphus as he is the best example of describing the human absurdity because of his being involved in the aimless repetition of rolling the boulder up to the hill, as humans always seek to find meaning in their lives but end up not finding that meaning, but the solution is to accept that situation by creating their own meaning and happiness. Khachiche argues that Sisyphus symbolizes humans, and the rock symbolizes life with its difficulties and problems, and the aimless repetition of the boulder up to the hill is the same as the repetition that humans do, like studies or works, as an example of suffering and punishment in this life. The only solution is to be conscious of the absurd, not to fear death, revolt against existence by existence itself, and be happy in every situation.

Dr. Nader Masarwah (May 2015, Vol. 3, No. 2, pp. 10-22), in his research, “The Use of Ancient Myths in Modern Poetry: The Myth of Sisyphus as a Case Study,” applies the ideas of Albert Camus’ Myth of Sisyphus as a case study on some of the modern poets like Al-Sayyāb, Al-Bayātī, Adonis, and ‘Abd al-‘Azīz al-Muqālīh, as well as the Palestinians Aḥmad Daḥbūr, Murīd al-Barghūthī, and Fārūq Muwāsī, and according to Masarwah, all of the above-mentioned poets use suffering and hope and the contemporary crisis of Arabs, and he highlights the modern poetry through the lens of ancient myth, specifically through the Myth of Sisyphus.

Michael Foley (2010), in his writing ‘The Age of Absurdity: Why Modern Life Makes it Hard to Be Happy,’ explores the concept of happiness in philosophy, spiritual teaching, and psychology, highlighting its challenges in a modern life of high expectations. He proposes the absurdity of the modern world and finding happiness in its challenges.

Research Methodology

In this research study, the qualitative method is used to explore the relationship of mobile phones' endless scrolling with the Sisyphus cycle of absurdity, as rolling a boulder up to the hill. A qualitative approach will be used for content analysis (Ali Shah, I. A., & Ahmad, G. 2021).

Textual Analysis

Textual analysis is used to analyze the qualitative data, such as the primary source, The Myth of Sisyphus by Albert Camus, and other related research papers and articles.

Data Collection

The primary source is the essay of Albert Camus’ The Myth of Sisyphus, specifically the story of Sisyphus, where he is condemned by the gods to continuously roll a boulder up a hill, only to watch it roll back down once he reaches the top, and how Sisyphus finds joy in this meaningless situation.

ANALYSIS—The Digital Echo of Sisyphus

The Camus philosophy is applied to examine the digital landscape through the core argument of the thesis by highlighting the exact references from Camus’ The Myth of Sisyphus. It was originally published in French in 1942 and later on translated into English by Justin O’Brien in 1955. Through close examination of the repetitive, endless, and purposeless use of smartphones, it seemed to be a digital form of absurdity in today’s modern era. It reflects in Camus’ Sisyphus, who is condemned to roll a boulder up to the hill in a cycle of endless and meaningless repetition yet seeks personal meaning and happiness despite that absurdity. Keeping in view, it is argued that the condition of mobile phone addiction is a contemporary enactment of absurdity by analyzing the direct quotations from Camus’ text and aligning them with the digital behaviors outlined in this study.

In the modern era, despite its technological advancement, mobile phone addiction and its endless scrolling in search of meaning and happiness make mobile phone addiction a contemporary Sisyphus cycle, and it is a lived experience of absurdity, theorized by Albert Camus in *The Myth of Sisyphus* (1942). The term “digital absurdity” refers to the modern manifestation of absurdity where individuals scroll endlessly throughout social media content, seeking meaning in platforms that don’t have a clear purpose. Albert Camus’ existential philosophy starts from the recognition of the fact that human beings innately seek meaning and purpose in a universe that lacks it (Camus, 1942, p. 28). Camus himself transforms the Greek mythological figure of a tragic hero into an existential paradigm in his work *The Myth of Sisyphus*, where Sisyphus is trapped in a situation of eternal punishment to roll a boulder up to the mountain only to watch it roll back down (Camus & O’Brien, 1991). Hence, it is critical in the comparison between the absurd labor of Sisyphus and the repetitive, compulsive behavior of modern smartphone users.

The Birth of Absurdity in the Digital Landscape

In the beginning of his book *The Myth of Sisyphus*, Albert Camus asks the most important philosophical question about life: Is life worth living? “*There is but one truly serious philosophical problem, and that is suicide. Judging whether life is or is not worth living amounts to answering the fundamental question of philosophy*” (Camus, 1942, p. 3).

The aforementioned statement introduces the base of absurdism that life has no meaning at all. In today's modern and digital era, mobile phone users are evidence of that behavior that echoes this absurd crisis—without any purpose, endlessly checking notifications, scrolling aimlessly, and participating in rituals lacking genuine and authentic meaning (Bennett, 2015). Despite knowing the fruitlessness and futility of keeping engaged with the devices, it exemplifies the absurd condition that Camus identifies. Albert Camus later explains absurdism as the clash between human searching/longing for meaning and the universe's silence and absence of it. “*The absurd is born of this confrontation between the human need and the unreasonable silence of the world*” (p. 28). Excessive and irresistible use of mobile phones mirrors this situation. As mobile phone users are seeking meaning, happiness, purpose, emotional satisfaction, or distraction from daily life problems and anxiety (Ali Shah, S. A., & Wali, M. I. 2021). On the other hand, the device offers shallow stimulation, wastes our time, and can't fulfill our desires in finding real-life satisfaction. Hence, the silence and meaningless results of mobile phones reflect the immense indifference described by Camus.

The Modern Sisyphus: Scrolling as Repetition

As Camus in his work describes the image of Sisyphus, eternally condemned to push a rock up to the hill, only to watch it roll back down. “*The workman of today works every day in his life at the same tasks, and this fate is no less absurd.*” (p. 121). In the modern age, this concept is replaced by the act of repetition and scrolling on mobile phones without resolution. The algorithm of social media feeds is designed as a never-ending and continuous process coming after one another; thus, each refresh hints at excitement, and each suggestion promises meaning, yet offering no excitement and meaning that mirror or replicate the everlasting descent of Sisyphus' boulder, which shows a cycle of expectation and emptiness (Beck & Ritter, 1992). Camus describes the endless labor of Sisyphus as not just a punishment but a metaphor for the human condition and existence. “*The struggle itself toward the heights is enough to fill a man's heart. One must imagine Sisyphus happy.*” (p. 123). According to Camus, knowing one's own situation is necessary, and awareness is the key to handling absurd situations.

Sisyphus is a hero according to Camus because his consciousness regarding his situation and yet his choice to embrace it openheartedly show his heroism. Facing absurdism is the best solution, according to him. Ask Sisyphus if the digital users, once they become aware of their entrapment in habitual patterns, also have a choice to resist distractions and external control by focusing on freedom, what's important, and being fully engaged in the present situation.

Consciousness, Repetition, and Alienation

Absurdity is not only a condition, but it is sudden feelings that emerge instantly in the face of routine. “*It happens that the stage sets collapse... But one day the 'why' arises and everything begins in that weariness tinged with amazement*” (p. 12). Most of the mobile phone users operate mobiles in an unconscious cycle of addiction until depression, anxiety, or existential boredom awakens. The fatigue after excessive use triggers the absurdity when they begin to question their addictive usage of mobile phones. Camus says, “*Weariness comes at the end of the acts of a mechanical life, but at the same time it inaugurates the impulse of consciousness*” (p. 12). The concept of weariness truly reflects the modern addiction studies. As awareness of being addictive is the first step toward detachment or disengagement. Here at this stage, after knowing one's addictive behavior, absurdism becomes a framework for recovery from that condition, as Camus' idea reflects that the absurd user, once conscious, can rebel against their fate.

The Absurd and the Illusion of Digital Fulfillment

Camus scrutinizes the absurd as a confrontation (a person struggles to find meaning in life, but the universe stays silent), and the absurd is not a quality of the world itself. It's a clash between our desires, like our demand for our needs, and the world's silence because of its lack of response and clarity regarding our questions. “*The absurd is essentially a divorce. It lies in neither of the elements compared; it is born of their confrontation*” (p. 30). In the

context of modern man, when users seek authenticity, connection, meaning, and validation, mobile phones offer algorithms of artificiality, impersonality, and the endless nature of digital interference. The disassociation between desiring and detachment shows absurdism. Camus introduced the term “collapse of illusion,” as he says, “*At any street corner the feeling of absurdity can strike any man in the face*” (p. 20). Similarly, in digital space, the moment when mobile users scroll all the way long in a situation that means nothing and brings no changes at all symbolizes digital absurdity.

Revolt as the Absurd Solution in the Digital Age

Camus introduced the term "lucid revolt" that rejects both false hopes and the ideology of nihilism. Nihilism refers to the concept that life has no meaning at all with any purpose and value. He also denies false hope, especially idealistic and religious ideologies regarding life after death (Turkle, S. 2011).

According to him, it is escaping from the reality, and he calls this “philosophical suicide”—pretending “meaning when there’s no evidence of it. The word "**lucid**" refers to full awareness with the evidence of naked eyes, and "**revolt**" refers to facing that reality bravely, living with courage and resistance. It is a kind of dignified resistance against absurdism (Fuchs, 2022). “*Revolt gives life its value. Spread out over the whole length of a life, it restores its majesty to that life*” (p. 55). In a digital context, completely discarding smartphones is not the solution, but as a revolt, using them consciously, holding control over them, refusing to be ruled by them, and reducing screen time can be the best way to manage absurdity. Camus emphasizes that “There is no fate that cannot be surmounted by scorn” (p. 121). The line is specifically convincing for addicted users of digital items. Just as Sisyphus owns his burden of eternally rolling the boulder up to the hill by embracing the situation with courage and defiance, mobile phone users can own their absurd situation by handling the algorithm of social media and its endless scrolling, rejecting and pretending meaninglessness, and avoiding overuse and misuse (Fuchs, C. 2017).

Conclusion: Imagining the Digital Sisyphus Happy

Albert Camus ends his essay with this paradoxical statement: “*The struggle itself toward the heights is enough to fill a man’s heart*” (p. 123). In a nutshell, this insight can guide digital users who, despite facing a seemingly meaningless routine, can find joy, meaning, and dignity by acknowledging and facing it (Postman, N. 1992).

Mobile phone addiction, then, is not just a psychological problem but also a philosophical confrontation with absurdity. By applying Albert Camus’ absurd reasoning to modern-day mobile phone addictive users, this analysis reframes modern users as a contemporary Sisyphus. Modern users obsessively scroll through a purposeless and meaningless digital existence, yet they are capable of revolt, awareness, and control to gain ultimate philosophical freedom.

Conclusion

The paper's aim is to highlight the absurdity of the modern era, using Albert Camus’ philosophy of absurdism as a theoretical framework. The Myth of Sisyphus as a primary source to examine the repetitive, purposeless, and addictive engagement with mobile phones as a modern replica of Sisyphus. The study demonstrates that mobile phone addiction mirrors the absurd struggle of Sisyphus, as both are trapped in an endless cycle of repetition yet fully conscious about its meaninglessness but continuing the act with acceptance and defiance.

The study shows that mobile phone addiction, particularly the endless scrolling in search of meaning and happiness, is a digital manifestation of absurdity. Users are trapped in social media algorithms and feeds, yet they recognize the futility of their behavior but remain locked in a cycle of repetition and engagement, just like Camus’ absurd man. The existential dissonance between human desire and the universe’s silence is highlighted as mobile phone users acknowledge their addictive behavior yet seek meaning, validation, or distraction from the device that ultimately offers no lasting satisfaction. After addressing the textual and philosophical analysis of the text, the study finds that mobile phone users, much like Sisyphus, find themselves in an endless cycle of purposeless scrolling. As Camus imagines Sisyphus happy, digital users also have the potential to revolt by becoming conscious of its absurd nature and resisting its control without quitting technology. Camus asserts that it is neither the world alone nor humanity that produces absurdity, but it provokes it in-between the two.

The findings pave the path for future researchers and addictive users of technology by offering a new philosophical framework to understand the psychological and emotional toll of digital addiction. It held up the mirror of absurdism to contemporary mobile users. Camus’ absurdist ideology, with the core themes of awareness,

revolt, and rejection of false hope, serves as a guide for digital mobile phone users to be aware, to regain control, to redefine their aims, and to face their condition with open eyes and wholeheartedly. Through the theoretical framework of absurdism, the study shows that the user who becomes aware of their condition and rebels against the endless algorithmic manipulation is not defeated by absurdity; they embrace it like Sisyphus and find meaning in the struggle itself.

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